

NDAC/LO/062

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Preprocessing of ESTEC IDT photon count runs (3)

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Input data

The third series of simulated IDT counts provided on magnetic tape from ESTEC (Letter by Vaghi, 1985 June 26; note by Davies, 1985 June 25) contains 90 frames for each of the following four runs:

- Run 1 - photon noise only
- Run 2 - photon noise + background effects
- Run 4 - same as Run 1, but using different seeds
- Run 5 - same as Run 2, but using different seeds

Note that Run 1 and 2 are probably not statistically independent, as the same seeds were used for the random number generators.

Only two different magnitudes appear, with equal probability: $B = 7.5$ ($I = 15239$ Hz) and $B = 12.5$ ($I = 152.4$ Hz).

Remark: Run 5 contains two empty frames (No. 30 and 31), while some of the samples in frames 29 and 32 do not correspond to any star in the observation sequence. For the latter samples, the simulations give the same counts as in the previous frame, rather than putting the count = 0 or simulating the background counts.

Preprocessing

The binning algorithm described in NDAC/LO/061 was used, with 45 bins and taking the phase at the centre of each bin as reference. (Some modifications of the previous routines were required in order to cope with the partially empty frames.)

Results

The complete results are available on magnetic tape in the format proposed in NDAC/LO/061. Tables 1 to 4 give the results for the first few frames in each run. Some summary statistics are given below.

Conclusions

These runs were specifically made for testing the accuracy of the preprocessing of very faint stars ($\lesssim 100$ photons/frame). It appears that the process works very well also in these cases and that the resulting phase dispersion is very close to the computed (Cramér-Rao) value.

Error distributions, bright stars

(i) Rms values of actual phase errors:

run number	$(\Delta p_0)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_1)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_2)_{\text{rms}}$
1	6.44 mas	6.99 mas	8.82 mas
2	6.15 mas	6.74 mas	8.59 mas
4	6.10 mas	6.18 mas	8.99 mas
5	5.32 mas	6.03 mas	7.63 mas

(ii) Rms values of normalized errors and of the transformed chi-square statistic t_1 (40 d.o.f.):

run number	$(t_1)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_0/\sigma_{p0})_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_1/\sigma_{p1})_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_2/\sigma_{p2})_{\text{rms}}$
1	0.958	1.332	1.488	1.003
2	0.968	1.307	1.484	0.947
4	1.046	1.050	1.004	1.031
5	1.064	0.965	1.004	0.925

Error distributions, faint stars

(i) Rms values of actual phase errors:

run number	$(\Delta p_0)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_1)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_2)_{\text{rms}}$
1	32.5 mas	33.0 mas	62.6 mas
2	43.3 mas	41.0 mas	91.8 mas
4	29.8 mas	32.0 mas	50.5 mas
5	36.2 mas	38.1 mas	71.2 mas

(ii) Rms values of normalized errors and test statistic t_1 :

run number	$(t_1)_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_0/\sigma_{p0})_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_1/\sigma_{p1})_{\text{rms}}$	$(\Delta p_2/\sigma_{p2})_{\text{rms}}$
1	0.988	0.993	0.949	1.203
2	0.929	0.960	0.936	1.414
4	1.021	0.980	0.977	1.126
5	0.853	0.996	0.960	1.231

Table 1. Beginning of result file for Run 1.

1	60	1152	130.4 11.7	91.9 17.1	23.9 15.4	.7832 .0333 .0282 .85	.7887 .0327 .0337 1.03	.7666 .0617 .0116 .19
1	59	1152	149.1 12.5	108.3 18.9	43.1 16.3	1.0827 .0254 .0381 1.82	1.0756 .0277 .0309 1.12	1.1041 .0363 .0595 1.64
-1	719	256	14985.3 265.4	11568.2 395.3	4037.9 345.1	1.0644 .0055 -.0041 .01 -.74	1.0615 .0057 -.0069 -1.20	1.0729 .0082 .0044 .54
2	60	1152	140.9 12.1	118.2 18.2	41.7 15.4	.7871 .0241 .0132 .55	.7845 .0251 .0107 .42	.7947 .0356 .0208 .58
2	59	1152	162.7 13.0	114.5 19.4	35.3 17.2	1.0416 .0277 -.0219 -1.24 -.79	1.0458 .0284 -.0177 -.62	1.0288 .0467 -.0347 -.74
-2	719	256	14776.5 263.5	11319.3 395.9	4461.2 342.6	1.0654 .0053 .0027 .33 .51	1.0672 .0057 .0045 .80	1.0598 .0074 -.0029 -.39
-3	719	2560	15239.2 84.5	11925.0 126.5	4409.6 109.8	1.0557 .0016 -.0013 -1.14 -.79	1.0566 .0018 -.0004 -.25	1.0531 .0024 -.0039 -1.63
-4	719	2560	15135.5 84.2	11804.6 126.0	4319.9 109.4	1.1512 .0017 .0016 .38 .94	1.1517 .0018 .0020 1.15	1.1498 .0024 .0002 .08
-5	719	2560	15370.9 84.9	11766.7 126.9	4375.7 110.6	1.1433 .0017 -.0006 2.84 -.38	1.1428 .0018 -.0011 -.63	1.1447 .0024 .0008 .32
-6	719	2560	15180.0 84.3	11738.5 126.0	4204.9 109.8	1.1399 .0017 .0016 .42 .97	1.1406 .0018 .0024 1.34	1.1376 .0025 -.0006 -.25
-7	719	2560	15136.2 84.2	11749.7 125.6	4101.1 109.6	1.1324 .0017 -.0001 -.73 -.04	1.1325 .0018 .0000 -.01	1.1323 .0026 -.0002 -.08
-8	719	2560	15224.0 84.5	11800.1 125.9	4097.1 109.9	.0156 .0017 -.0016 1.65 -.93	.0151 .0018 -.0020 -1.13	.0169 .0026 -.0002 -.10

Table 2. Beginning of result file for Run 2.

1	60	1152	200.4 14.5	102.0 21.5	53.7 19.8	.7671 .0302 .0121	.7742 .0359 .0192	.7458 .0353 -.0092
					-1.65	.40	.53	-.26
1	59	1152	230.5 15.3	153.1 23.4	69.3 20.6	1.0724 .0219 .0278	1.0688 .0247 .0242	1.0830 .0285 .0384
					2.09	1.27	.98	1.35
-1	719	256	15108.5 266.5	11808.4 397.1	4208.5 345.6	1.0627 .0053 -.0057	1.0593 .0056 -.0091	1.0730 .0079 .0046
					.42	-1.07	-1.62	.58
2	60	1152	218.1 15.1	122.8 22.7	58.8 20.3	.8156 .0262 .0417	.8202 .0302 .0464	.8016 .0332 .0277
					-.78	1.59	1.54	.83
2	59	1152	220.1 15.2	108.7 22.5	41.9 20.7	1.0562 .0316 -.0073	1.0599 .0354 -.0036	1.0451 .0474 -.0184
					-.15	-.23	-.10	-.39
-2	719	256	14895.8 264.6	11750.8 396.2	4339.2 342.4	1.0645 .0052 .0018	1.0679 .0056 .0052	1.0540 .0076 -.0087
					.55	.33	.94	-1.15
-3	719	2560	15294.0 84.7	11889.6 126.5	4298.1 110.1	1.0557 .0017 -.0013	1.0562 .0018 -.0008	1.0541 .0025 -.0029
					-1.15	-.79	-.46	-1.17
-4	719	2560	15238.1 84.5	11830.6 126.4	4339.3 109.9	1.1508 .0017 .0012	1.1511 .0018 .0014	1.1502 .0024 .0005
					.06	.72	.80	.22
-5	719	2560	15380.8 84.9	11743.3 127.1	4410.2 110.7	1.1427 .0017 -.0012	1.1424 .0018 -.0015	1.1438 .0024 -.0002
					2.46	-.71	-.85	-.07
-6	719	2560	15179.5 84.3	11723.2 125.8	4136.7 109.8	1.1400 .0017 .0018	1.1404 .0018 .0022	1.1390 .0026 .0008
					.08	1.07	1.20	.32
-7	719	2560	15222.4 84.5	11826.7 126.0	4081.6 109.9	1.1322 .0017 -.0003	1.1323 .0018 -.0002	1.1318 .0026 -.0007
					-.44	-.20	-.13	-.27
-8	719	2560	15327.2 84.7	11826.0 126.3	4094.7 110.4	.0161 .0017 -.0010	.0155 .0018 -.0016	.0180 .0026 .0008
					1.24	-.59	-.90	.32

Table 3. Beginning of result file for Run 4.

1	60	2048	143.4 9.2	118.5 13.7	46.8 11.8	1.1760 .0177 -.0030 .05	1.1794 .0191 .0004 .02	1.1660 .0242 -.0130 -.54
-1	731	512	15163.0 188.8	10751.8 282.7	4252.7 249.3 -1.44	.5580 .0040 .0003 .07	.5556 .0044 -.0021 -.49	.5652 .0056 .0075 1.33
2	60	2048	144.1 9.2	98.2 13.4	18.0 12.2 .29	1.1998 .0284 .0019 .07	1.2019 .0244 .0041 .17	1.1932 .0650 -.0047 -.07
-2	731	512	15304.4 189.7	11955.2 284.4	4287.5 246.9 .09	.5488 .0037 -.0032 -.86	.5492 .0039 -.0028 -.72	.5477 .0055 -.0043 -.78
3	60	2048	162.8 9.8	114.9 14.2	33.2 12.9 1.16	1.1747 .0218 -.0297 -1.36	1.1730 .0222 -.0315 -1.42	1.1799 .0374 -.0245 -.66
-3	731	512	15187.4 188.9	11265.2 282.5	4031.4 248.4 2.00	.5363 .0039 -.0100 -2.54	.5365 .0042 -.0098 -2.34	.5357 .0059 -.0105 -1.79
-4	731	2560	15243.2 84.5	10874.2 125.8	3833.3 111.5 .27	.6384 .0018 -.0005 -.29	.6395 .0020 .0005 .27	.6352 .0028 -.0037 -1.33
-5	731	512	15452.9 190.6	11591.8 285.5	4427.6 249.2 2.37	.6317 .0038 -.0015 -.40	.6329 .0041 -.0004 -.09	.6283 .0054 -.0049 -.91
5	59	2048	159.3 9.7	101.2 14.2	33.6 12.9 -.14	.0124 .0226 -.0055 -.24	.0000 .0244 -.0179 -.74	.0497 .0368 .0317 .86
-6	731	512	15297.4 189.6	10948.2 283.3	4031.1 249.8 .91	.6233 .0040 -.0042 -1.05	.6247 .0043 -.0028 -.65	.6190 .0060 -.0085 -1.43
6	59	2048	156.3 9.6	100.1 14.4	52.5 12.7 -1.20	.0264 .0201 -.0104 -.52	.0275 .0232 -.0094 -.40	.0233 .0233 -.0135 -.58
-7	731	48	15384.2 622.6	10896.9 932.4	3306.4 836.4 -1.08	.6279 .0138 .0061 .44	.6241 .0141 .0023 .16	.6392 .0235 .0174 .74

Table 4. Beginning of result file for Run 5.

-1	715	896	218.5 17.1	126.3 24.0	40.1 22.9	1.1590 .0303 .0175 .89	1.1217 .0367 -.0198 -.54	1.2709 .0547 .1295 2.37
-1	714	256	15506.6 269.8	11340.8 401.5	3934.4 354.7	.9191 .0057 .0016 -.19	.9206 .0060 .0031 .51	.9147 .0087 -.0028 -.33
-1	713	256	15141.1 266.9	10946.1 399.1	3975.3 351.9	.2889 .0057 .0011 -.12	.2914 .0061 .0035 .58	.2816 .0084 -.0063 -.75
1	61	112	14766.7 398.1	10515.6 588.6	3820.4 519.3	1.1876 .0090 .0049 -.05	1.1874 .0097 .0047 .48	1.1882 .0134 .0055 .41
1	60	1040	223.7 16.1	97.8 23.3	22.8 22.2	.0130 .0439 .0431 .87	.0082 .0434 .0383 .88	.0274 .0935 .0575 .62
-2	715	1024	209.6 15.7	77.5 22.8	26.7 21.7	1.1388 .0474 .0031 -1.12	1.1428 .0531 .0071 .13	1.1269 .0785 -.0088 -.11
-2	714	256	15038.8 265.9	11475.9 397.9	4027.6 347.4	.9128 .0054 .0010 1.11	.9172 .0057 .0054 .94	.8995 .0082 -.0123 -1.50
-2	713	256	15489.3 269.8	11597.2 404.9	4618.3 353.2	.2737 .0053 -.0084 -.04	.2744 .0057 -.0078 -1.36	.2719 .0073 -.0102 -1.40
2	60	1024	247.0 17.0	159.1 25.2	67.9 22.5	.0196 .0236 .0309 .49	.0079 .0268 .0192 .72	.0547 .0318 .0659 2.07
-3	715	640	230.5 20.8	85.7 29.6	10.2 28.9	1.1307 .0843 .0007 -.99	1.1647 .0655 .0347 .53	1.0285 .2707 -.1015 -.37
-3	714	256	15492.0 269.8	10926.3 404.2	4268.2 356.3	.9026 .0056 -.0035 .53	.9038 .0061 -.0023 -.38	.8990 .0080 -.0071 -.88
-3	713	256	15348.9 268.6	11118.8 402.0	4281.7 353.4	.2642 .0055 -.0123 .41	.2649 .0060 -.0116 -1.93	.2620 .0079 -.0145 -1.83